
Design of Electro-adhesive Gripper for handling of Carbon Fibre sheets

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Abstract:

With the advent of composite materials, industrial tools for their manufacturing have progressed as well. In handling of cut fabrics involved in composite manufacturing methods, due to the unconstrained nature of the fabric edges, they are susceptible to fraying and disorientation. This can be avoided by use of robotic grippers, that do not use positive locking, or high vacuum pressures. One such gripping method may be electro-adhesion, where localized charge distribution aids in polarizing the fabric which in turn is attracted to the gripper. This paper analyses the ponderomotive pressure developed by such a gripper for a range of values for the number of electrode pairs and the electrode lengths. Optimization of parameters for maximizing the ponderomotive pressure in the constrained contact area of gripper is needed. Two test geometry cases of the picked fabric are considered, to observe the performance of the gripper in picking large sheets, as well as small cut fabrics. The best possible combination of the electrode length and number of electrode pairs is then applied to the test geometry cases. The designed gripper shows a maximum fabric sag of 0.55mm on the geometry cases, which does not contribute to develop a matrix distortion of a large magnitude on the picked fabric object. Such a gripper assembly can be mounted on an articulated robot to pick and place parts of the cut fabric.

Keywords: Electro-adhesion, Woven Composite Material Handling, Ponderomotive Pressure, Contigutive Gripper, Robot End Effector

I. INTRODUCTION

The use of composites in structural components is certainly a welcome change, and is being appreciated by both engineers and members of student technical teams worldwide. However, a major problem observed during manufacturing of components using composite materials is the fraying and distortion of the woven matrix, especially in the case of raw composite fibres, where the woven fabric has not been placed in epoxy. While manufacturers of these composite materials usually take care to avoid such problems, mainly by stitching the edges of the fabric to reduce

fraying, this cannot be ensured after the fabric has been cut to suite the design geometry. Thus, a large amount of material is either wasted, or product quality is forsaken. To avoid these problems, a material handling device is necessary to handle these cut sheets of carbon fibre without fraying or distorting the weave. Ponderomotive pressure associated with electro-adhesion is the pressure developed due to forces emerging because of polarization. This polarization is generated by the application of an electric field to a dielectric volume. The principle of electroadhesion has been explored to a great degree, especially in the field of soft robotics as methods for adhesion to vertical and more than obtuse surfaces to allow robots to climb and explore different terrains. The advent of manufacturing processes such as photolithography has allowed engineers to design these coils on soft and reasonable pliable materials, hence giving the product a shape compliant aspect as well. Such an electro-adhesive coil would make for a suitable gripper to handle composite materials, as this would entail zero use of positive locking, and thus reduce the risk of distorting the composite matrix. In electro-adhesion principle, with the application of voltages in the range of a few kilo-volts, ponderomotive pressures in the range of kilopascals can be achieved. This makes the principle of electro-adhesion quite useful for industrial applications. Electro-adhesive coils on pliable surfaces have been explored primarily for their shape compliance. Whereas such a shape compliance may not always be necessary, if the geometry of the item to be gripped is known. An ideal electro-adhesive entity is made of three parts:

- A substrate - usually pliable to aid shape compliance
- The coils - usually made of copper and have very low thickness to allow deflection without failure
- The dielectric - a medium which coats the coils and is the surface which physically contacts the gripped body

While positive locking can most definitely distort a composite weave, another cause of distortion is deformation, or deflection. Consider a thought experiment, where a plain cotton napkin is placed on the palm of one's hand, and is picked up from the center. Most definitely, the napkin will be inferred that shape compliance to such an extent is detrimental, and hence the substrate can be replaced with a rigid body, making the manufacturing of such a gripper as easy as manufacturing a printed circuit board.

J. Guo et. al. (1) propose a research methodology for the performance evaluation of different electro-adhesive pad geometries. The methodology ponders a cost-effective pad design and manufacturing process, based on solid ink printing, chemical etching and conformal coating, and a mechatronics-based testing platform. Their method compares the pad in two cases, with the varying substrate materials as glass and aluminium. Their results compare coil geometries, and show an increase in electro-adhesion force with the glass substrate between 1 and 28%, and for the aluminium substrate an increase of 5 to 12%

Kisuk Choi et. al (2) postulate an empirical equation for the electro-adhesive force developed by a gripper, based on the popular Maxwell Equation. Their equation involves “electrode areal fraction”, the “boundary edge ratio” and the impedance. Electrode areal fraction is the electrode surface area divided by the area of the electro-adhesive device. The boundary edge ratio is the ratio of the length of the electrodes to the perimeter of the device.

G J Monkman (3) demonstrates a range of robot gripping techniques suitable for use with carbon and glass fibre sheets. It defines appropriate gripping techniques for desired tasks considering the material structure of the composite sheet. It classifies the gripping techniques as impactive, ingressive, contiguous and astrictive. Impactive methods use conventional robotic grippers such as two or three fingered claws or chucks, where the gripper closes around the object, or from within the object in case of structures similar to hollow cylinders. Ingressive, or intrusive methods rely on positive locking. Contiguous grippers require the gripping surface to make direct contact with the object to develop a gripping force, Lastly, astrictive grippers provide a gripping force without initial direct contact.

K. M. Digumurti et. al. (4) demonstrates the application of electro-adhesion for crawling robots, and postulates a simplified mathematical equation for the normal force exerted by an electro-adhesive gripper. Joni Mici et. al.(5) explores coil geometries for layered geometries for microelectronics. Coil geometries are individually analysed, and a 2x2 array is manufactured to test lifting of voxels made of copper, aluminum and a polymer. It also tests the reliability of gripping, by testing for misalignment. D. Ruffato et. al. (6) design an electro-adhesive gripper as a robust mechanism for perching, climbing and gripping applications. A simplified mathematical model is proposed, irrespective of the coil geometry, which is entirely dependent on the magnitude of the resultant polarization on gripped material, and the generated electric field strength. The author compares a combinations of electrode count, electrode widths and gaps at a constant electrode length and thickness. These combinations are tested on a 6-DOF Force torque sensor and an air slide with variable pressure, so quantify the adhesive and shear force.

N. Gorbach et. al. (7) prove a mathematical model for an electro-adhesive gripper, based on the nature of the material picked. The material is classified into either a conductor or a dielectric, and the mathematical models are altered accordingly. For the conductive material model, the normal force generated is proved to be unrelated to the electric field and the polarization on the material surface and instead depends entirely on the applied voltage, the gap between the interdigitated coils and the area of contact. For the dielectric material model, an equation similar to (8) is observed.

Thus, it can be observed that the principle of electroadhesion has been explored to a great degree. However, application specific investigation of their performance and usability is yet to be explored, specifically in the composites manufacturing domain. Electro-adhesive grippers must be explored, not as an alternative, but as a promising replacement to current composite woven

material handling systems. In this exploration, optimisation of the ponderomotive pressure in a restricted contact area is necessary, as the size of the gripper may not always be scaled to the size of the gripped sheet.

II.MATERIALS

The primary components of the gripper are the substrate, the coils and the dielectric insulator. As the gripper needs to be rigid by itself, to discourage sagging action of picked fabric under the influence of gravity, a rigid substrate needed to be considered. Hence, the substrate used is FR4, which is the standard material for printed circuit boards. This also greatly reduced the complexity of manufacturing the gripper, as manufacturing the coils can be simplified as a PCB etching task. For the dielectric material, polyimide was chosen due to ease of procurement and assembly, as it is available in the form of tape, which can be carefully applied on the copper side of the PCB. For all future analyses, the following material properties were considered (**Error! Reference source not found.**)

Table I: Material Properties used in FEA Models

Material	Relative Permeability	Density (kg/m ³)	Young's Modulus (GPa)	Poisson's Ratio	Electrical Conductivity (S/m)
Copper	1	8490	126	0.34	5.998x 10 ⁷
FR4	4.5	1900	22	0.15	0.004
Polyimide (9)	3.4	1420	2.5	0.34	1.5x10 ⁷
Carbon Fiber (10)	1.5	-	1000	0.1	-

III.METHODOLOGY

The gripper was designed by first identifying an optimum coil type, then identifying the optimum parameters for the identified coil type, and then subject this optimized coil to a set of load cases to observe its behavior for charge decay and pressure generated by application of suitable voltage.

Figure 1: Circular Coil

Figure 2: Square/Rectangular Coil

Figure 3: Circular Concentric Coil

i. Coil Choice

Three coil geometries were considered. Variant A (Figure 1) is circular and convoluted, variant B (Figure 2) is rectangular and interdigitated and variant C (Figure 3) has concentric electrodes. For coil variant A, the coil cannot be defined parametrically to change the length of the electrode and the number of electrode pairs. Also, for irregular geometries, it cannot be scaled appropriately to cover the entirety of the picked object in the sense that a lot of the coil area will be left uncovered, therefore leading to losses. Hence, it was discarded from the FEA models. For geometry C, the number of electrode pairs could be changed dynamically, and the length of the electrode need not be defined due to its concentric nature. However, it cannot be scaled for irregular objects without incurring losses. Finally, geometry B was identified as perfectly scalable and was easily defined. The geometry can be scaled to suit thin and wide objects alike, merely by changing the orientation of the coil and by altering the electrode length and count. This geometry was also easily definable, using simple array functions to replicated the electrodes for the required count. Therefore, this coil geometry was used to perform FEA and observe results. To perform the optimization studies, the number of electrode pairs (N) and the length of the electrode (L) were varied, keeping the values for the electrode width and electrode gap constant at 2.5mm and 0.6mm respectively

A representation of the electrode width, electrode length, dielectric gap and an electrode pair is shown in Figure 4

Figure 4: Geometric Representation of the coil parameters of the gripper

Figure 5: Gripper-fabric geometry used for the optimization studies

ii.FEA Models

COMSOL Multiphysics was used to model, analyze and optimize the coil geometries. A 200x200x1.5mm thick cuboid of FR4 was considered to act as the substrate. On this cuboid, a parametric sketch was made, defining the number of electrode pairs (N), the electrode width, the gap between the interdigitated electrodes and the electrode lengths (L). This was a key operation, as this was allowed for dynamic geometry updates. Once the coil sketch was made, it was extruded by the electrode thickness to form the solid electrode geometry. Another square block of 200x200x1mm was generated, and a Boolean operation was used to create the domain for the insulating dielectric. Thus, the geometry for the gripper was completed. For the initial identification of the optimum electrode length and electrode pair count, a 500x500mm sheet of Carbon fiber was considered, and the gripper was placed on it centrally, as is shown in Figure 5

iii.Load Case

After finalizing the geometry, the Solid Mechanics and Electrostatics libraries were used to analyze the model. In the Electrostatics load case, equal and opposite electric potentials were applied on the electrode surface, and the rest of the bodies were given the charge conservation constraint. For the Solid Mechanics load case, the gripper assembly was given a fixed constraint, allowing the gripper to be fixed, and the carbon fiber sheet to move and deform as physically required. The projection of the coil area was created as a separate surface on the carbon fiber sheet, on which a boundary load was applied, with a pressure computed from the previous electrostatics module. This allowed for the force applied at every mesh node on that surface to be defined from the electrostatics module, and a more accurate result to be obtained. Lastly, a gravity was defined along the Z axis, to simulate gravity.

In the case of such contiguous grippers, a decay period needs to be observed to allow for the generated polarization on the gripped object to be dissipated, and this time period needs to be studied as well. However, these results will not be discussed in this paper.

iv. Gripper Mount

The mount was primarily designed as a method to hold the PCB in place while supporting the weight of the gripped item. Since the gripped item has so little weight, material choices could be widened to suit insulation from electrical hazards. Hence, for both the mount and the shroud, bakelite was chosen as the material.

Figure 6: Gripper Mount Geometry

Figure 7: Gripper with its shroud

The PCB can be fastened to the mount using standard M4 screws, and the mount can be fastened to an external structure along with the shroud using another set of M4 screws. No direct electrical contact is allowed between the robotic structure and PCB coil.

IV.MATHEMATICAL MODEL

According to N. Gorbach, the mathematical model for the generated force for an electro-adhesive gripper can be given by two equations:

$$F = \frac{\epsilon_0 \epsilon_r A V^2}{2d^2} \quad (7)$$

Where,

ϵ_0 is the electric constant

ϵ_r is the relative electric permeability

A is the contact area

V is the applied voltage

d is the dielectric width, i.e. the gap in the interdigitated electrodes

The above model is applicable for conductive picked objects. As raw carbon fiber does not classify as a conductor, a modified mathematical model is required, based on the electric field and polarization. The electric field strength is the ratio of the magnitude of a charge placed in the electric field, to the force experienced by it. The polarization on the surface of the carbon fiber sheet is given as

$$P = (\epsilon_r - 1)E$$

P = Polarization developed on material

E = Electric Field Strength

ϵ_r = Dielectric Constant

This model is stated as,

$$\sigma = P \times E \quad (7)$$

Where, σ is called the ponderomotive pressure

This second model was used to evaluate the adhesion force for the designed electro-adhesive gripper.

V.RESULTS

i. Identification of Optimum N and L

The values for the generated Electric field strength, developed polarization and the ponderomotive pressure were recorded in the form of a table, for the varied values of N and L. The electrode pairs were varied from a value of 1 to 17, with electrode lengths varying from 10 to 175 mm, in steps of 5mm. Accordingly, the following surface plots were generated:

The aim of this optimization study is to identify a value for N and L that generates the maximum possible ponderomotive pressure. As is observed in the plots (Figure 8), the region from 14 to 17 electrode pairs, of 110 to 175mm generates a high magnitude of this pressure.

Figure 8: Electric Field Magnitude for considered values of N and L

Focussing on this region suggests that the combination of 15 electrode pairs of 165mm length is optimum. The reason these plots are considered fair is that all of these combinations were subjected to the same applied voltage of 100V. For the final iteration of the gripper, a voltage of 5kV will be considered as an arbitrary value. The reason this particular value is chosen is that literature states that the applied voltage can range in the order of 10kV. However, arcing is definite possibility, which cannot be observed without physical testing. Hence, a relatively moderate value of applied voltage was chosen.

Figure 9: Ponderomotive Pressure for considered values of N and L

ii. Variation of Ponderomotive Pressure with Voltage

The values of the generated polarization, electric field and the corresponding ponderomotive pressure were observed by varying the applied voltage on the obtained optimised model. These simulation results were mainly observed to verify them with the mathematical model. From these results, a curve was generated the basis of which, an appropriate applied voltage can be identified considering the load to be lifted.

The polarization and electric field strength are observed to increase with an increase in voltage, as they are directly related.

Figure 10: Developed Electric Field vs. Applied Voltage

Figure 11: Developed Polarization vs. Applied Voltage

However, the relation in the ponderomotive pressure is not observed to be a straight line, but similar to a square relation, which corresponds with the mathematical model.

Figure 12: Developed Ponderomotive Pressure vs Applied Voltage

From the above curve (Figure 12), it can be inferred that a voltage of an extremely large magnitude need not be necessary for our scope, as the weight of raw carbon fibre sheets is very less. Hence, for both the geometry cases, a relatively low voltage of 250V was used.

iii. Testing on Sample Fabric Geometries

a. Fabric Geometry Case 1

For geometry case 1 shown in Figure 13, a rectangular sheet of carbon fibre, 1 x 5 m was considered, to mimic specifically cut sheets of the fabric in mass material vending industries. Here, it is assumed that the edges have not been constrained by means such as a thread stitch, or masking tape. Thus, the sheet at this stage is susceptible to distortion and fraying.

Figure 13: Geometry Case 1, with grippers placed in a 2x6 array

A 2x6 array of grippers was considered to hold the sheet. The optimum combination of electrode length and electrode pairs was used, at a voltage of 250V. As is observed from Figure 14, a maximum deflection of 0.55~ mm is observed, which results in an almost negligible distortion in the woven matrix. Thus, the designed gripper can be said to pass this case.

Figure 14: Deflection plot for geometry case 1

b. Fabric Geometry Case 2

For geometry case 2 shown in Figure 15, a randomly shaped cut sheet of carbon fibre was considered, to mimic specifically cut parts at the end-user assembly facility. Here, due to the irregular shape, stitching to constrain the edges cannot be feasible due to the unknown and possibly tedious nature of the edges, and masking tape cannot be applied further due to its size.

Figure 15: Geometry Case 2 (Randomly shaped cut fabric)

Here, two combinations of the coil were considered; the optimum variant and a scaled version of the coil to better suit the area of the carbon fibre part in contact. As is observed in both cases, shown in Figure 16 and Figure 17, the maximum deflection

Figure 16: Deflection: Combination scaled to suite picked part

Figure 17: Deflection: Obtained optimised combination

of the sheet is in the order of 10–10 mm, which cannot contribute to the woven matrix distortion in a large magnitude. Thus, the designed gripper can be said to have passed this test case.

VI.CONCLUSION

The principle of electro-adhesion has a definite place in the material handling industry, especially in the composites channel. Electro-adhesive grippers can most definitely replace pneumatic suction type grippers for such loose fabrics, and their geometry can be adapted for a particularly irregular shape. to the low magnitude of their picked loads, the system can be made designed to be reasonably lightweight. Simple manufacturing methods like etching can make these grippers low cost, and thus easily replaceable. The designed gripper shows a maximum deflection of 0.55mm in geometry case 1, and a deflection in the order of 10–10 mm in geometry case 2, therefore causing a minimum, if not negligible distortion in the woven matrix of the picked sheets. Thus, the designed gripper can be said to have achieved its goal in gripping sheets to cause minimum matrix distortion, and shows the potential applications of electro-adhesion in the composite manufacturing industry. As a further study in the topic, the decay of charges due to polarization after the gripper is powered off can be observed, and geometry optimizations can be performed to reduce the dwell time.

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